

Proximate Composition of Hatchery Waste Meal and Its Utilization in Broiler Diet

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Abstract

The study was carried out to explore the nutritional value of Hatchery Waste Meal (HWM) and to find a more economical and sustainable means of its utilization in poultry industry. The research was set to determine the proximate composition and the replacement value of HWM as protein source at 5% and 10% levels of inclusion using 120 Marshall broiler strains in a completely randomized design which lasted for the period of 4 weeks. Performance parameters measured were; Initial Live Weight (ILW), Final Live Weight (FLW), Daily Feed intake (DFI), Total Weight Gain (TWG) and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR). Feed and water were offered *ad libitum* while mortality was recorded as it occurred. The data collected was analysed using one way analysis of variance procedure of IBM SPSS. Results of the proximate composition showed that HWM contained crude protein (23.12%), ash (66.05%), phosphorous (0.43%), crude fibre (2.59%), moisture (0.18%), calcium (7.69%), hence a good source of protein, calcium and phosphorus for poultry. Performance results showed that FLW, TWG and FCR were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) among the treatments. Broilers fed diet 2 (5% HWM) and 4 (commercial diet) had superior FLW (2296.67g and 2371.67g); TWG (1440.22g and 1538.34g); and FCR (2.01 and 1.83) respectively. However, no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed in ILW at the onset of the experiment and DFI at the end of the experiment. It could be concluded that inclusion of 5% HWM in the diet of finisher broiler chicken promotes optimum performance.

Keywords: Broiler, Composition, Hatchery Waste, Performance

1.0 Introduction

The most critical challenge facing poultry production in Nigeria is the cost of conventional feed stuffs particularly protein sources [1]. This has resulted in the continuous abandonment of the poultry business as a result of consistent inability to break even throughout the production process in both broiler and layer enterprises [1, 14]. It was reported that feed account for 60-70% of the total cost of broiler production [2, 15]. Therefore, a shift to alternative sources of ingredients, especially non-conventional sources may help particularly when the ingredients are cheaply available.

Hatchery waste meal is rich in protein but has not gotten serious attention in terms of utilization

in Nigeria [3]. According to Sharara et al. [4], hatchery waste contains 43 – 71% moisture, 33.1% protein, 29.0% ether extract, 12.1% crude fibre, 21.5% ash and 28.8 MJ/kg of gross energy. Similarly, Ilian and Salman [5] reported that hatchery waste contains 22.8% crude protein, 21.48% true protein, 22.64% Ca and 2706 kcal kg⁻¹ metabolisable energy. On the use of Hatchery Waste Meal (HWM) in broiler chicken, Mehdipour [6] reported no significant difference in the body weight of broiler for starters, growers and total period of the experiment for broiler groups fed (0%, 1.5%, 3% and 4.5%) HWM. However, the same authors reported significant difference in feed intake and feed conversion ratio in the total period of the experiment. Abiola et al. [7] reported significant difference in weight gain of broiler chicken fed 0%, 10%,

20% and 30% whole hatchery waste meal as replacement for fish meal, with 0%, 10% and 20% replacement levels been superior ($p < 0.05$) in weight gains than 30% replacement level. This study was conducted to explore the proximate composition of hatchery waste meal and the effects of its utilization in broiler finisher diet.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 The Study Area

The experiment was conducted at the poultry production and research unit of the Department of Animal science, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero, located (Lat. $12^{\circ} 18' 18''$ N, Long. $4^{\circ} 29' 52''$ E and Alt. 266.2m above sea level) in the North West zone of Nigeria. The entire state experiences two alternating seasons: the short wet (rainy) season; which start in May/June and ends in September, and the long dry season; which complete the remaining parts of the year. The average annual rainfall is 750mm [8]. The open Savanna vegetation pattern in the area provided opportunity for extensive livestock production system and cultivation of short duration arable crops. Thus, most of the people in the area are agro-pastoralists: producing crops like maize, millet, sorghum, groundnut mostly in the wet season and crops like onion, tomatoes and pepper in the dry season, while animals such as cattle, sheep, goat, and poultry species are kept throughout the year.

2.2 Preparation of Hatchery Waste

The hatchery waste was boiled for 15 minutes to destroy any possible microbial contaminants such as *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella species*, which are readily destroyed by heat. It was then broken to pieces and sun-dried for 48 hrs. The waste was further crushed and dried again for 24 hrs and finely ground. The ground poultry hatchery waste was taken to Animal Care laboratory for proximate composition analysis prior to its incorporation into the experimental diets at various levels.

2.3 Proximate Analyses of Hatchery Waste Meal

The Poultry hatchery waste meal was analyzed for moisture content, nitrogen, ether extract, crude fibre and Nitrogen-Free Extract (NFE)

according to the procedures of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists [9].

Moisture was determined by weighing 2g of the sample in Al dishes and oven drying of the sample at 135°C for 2 hrs. The samples were shaken for even distribution. With the covers removed the dishes and covers were quickly placed in the oven. After 2 hrs, the covers were placed on the dishes and transferred to desiccator to cool. Weight loss of the sample was calculated as moisture lost.

For protein determination, weight of the sample (0.250-1.000 g) was placed into the digestion flask and 16.7 g K_2SO_4 , 0.01 g anhydrous CuSO_4 , 0.6 TiO_2 , 0.3 g pumice, 0.5-1.0 g Alundum granules, and 20 mL H_2SO_4 were added with additional 1.0 mL H_2SO_4 for each 0.2 of the organic matter if sample weight is > 1 g. The flask was heated at 5 minutes boil rate until dense white fumes clear bulb of flask, it was swirled gently and heated continuously for additional 90 minutes. The mixture was cooled and 250 mL H_2O was added and cooled to room temperature. Accurately measured amount of standard acid was added to the volume of H_2O such that condenser tip was sufficiently immersed. 3-4 drops of indicator solution were added. In order to reduce forming, 2-4 drops of tributyl was added to the digestion flask, another 0.5 - 1.0 g alundum granules was added. Sufficient NaOH solution was added such that the mixture became strongly alkaline. Distillation apparatus was immediately connected and distillation was carried out at 7.5 minutes boil rate until ≥ 150 mL distillate was collected in titration beaker. Excess standard acid in distillate was titrated with standard NaOH solution.

Calculation of % N:

$$\% \text{ N} = \left[(N_{\text{acid}}) (mL_{\text{acid}}) - (mL_{\text{bk}}) (N_{\text{NaOH}}) - (mL_{\text{NaOH}}) (N_{\text{NaOH}}) [1400.67] \right] / \text{mg sample}$$

Ether extract was determined by extracting 2 g sample dried with anhydrous ether. Thimble with porosity permitting rapid passage of ether was used. Extraction period varied from 4 hrs at condensation rate of 5 – 6 drops/sec to 16 hrs at 2 – 3 drops/sec. Extract was dried for 30 mins at 100° , cooled and weighed.

Crude fibre was determined by ext 2 g ground sample with ether and transferring it to 600 mL reflux beaker, avoiding fibre contamination. Bumping granules (0.25-0.5 g) was added followed by 200 mL near boiling 1.25% H₂SO₄ solution in small stream directly on the sample and laced on digestion apparatus at 5 mins intervals and boiled for 30 minutes rotating beaker periodically. At the end of refluxing, near boiling H₂O was allowed to flow through a funnel to warm it; and then the liquid was decanted through the funnel, washing solids. It was filtered to dryness using 25 mm vacuum. The residue was washed with 40 – 50 mL of near boiling H₂O, filtering after each washing. Residue from funnel was washed into reflux beaker with near boiling 1.25% NaOH solution. Near boiling water was allowed to flow through crucible to warm it. The residue was washed with near boiling 1.25% H₂SO₄ solution and then with two 25 – 30 mL portions near boiling H₂O and filtered after each washing. The crucible with the residue was dried for 2 hrs at 130 ± 2°, cooled in desiccator and weighed. The dried residue was set to ash at 550 ± 10°, cooled in desiccator and weighed.

% Crude fibre = Loss in weight on ignition × 100 / weight of sample.

Calcium and Phosphorus were determined according to AOAC 2005 [10] by taking 2.0g of the dried sample of HWM in a digestion flask and 20ml of acid mixture (650ml conc. HNO₃; 80ml perchloric acid; 20ml conc. H₂SO₄) was added, the flask was heated until a clear digest was obtained. The digest was diluted with distilled water to the 50ml mark.

For phosphorus determination, 50ml of the above sample digest was collected and 1 drop of phenolphthalein indicator was added. 1ml of sulphuric acid solution and 0.4g of ammonium persulfate was added. The solution was boiled gently for a period of 30-40minutes until total volume left was 10ml, the solution was cooled, and 1 drop of phenolphthalein was added and the solution neutralized to faint pink colour with 1N sodium hydroxide. The solution was then made up to 50ml with distilled water, and then tested for total phosphorus.

Total phosphorus content was determined after 50 ml of the above solution was pipette into an acid cleaned dry 125ml Erlenmeyer flask. One drop of phenolphthalein indicator was added and 8.0ml of

combined reagent was added and mixed thoroughly. It was allowed to stand for at least 10 minutes for colour development. The absorbance was measured at 880nm using a reagent blank to zero the spectrophotometer. This was conducted thrice and the average absorbance value for the sample was taken.

For calcium determination, the solution of the ash of the sample of HWM was aspirated into Varian AA240 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer and was heated to atomize the element. A beam of radiation was passed, and the absorbance of the sample was taken. The machine runs in triplicate and the average absorbance of the sample was calculated by referring to the appropriate calibration curve drawn by the inbuilt computer interface. The concentrations were equally read out from the print-out from the computer.

Nitrogen-Free Extract (NFE) was calculated as:

% NFE = 100% - (% EE + % CP + % Ash + % CF + % Moisture)

2.3 Management of the birds

The sum of one hundred and twenty (120) 21 day-old broiler chicks (Marshall Strains) were used in the experiment. The experimental birds were raised in deep litter housing units. Appropriate Medication and vaccination were administered as at when due in clean and disinfected pens. Mortality was recorded as it occurred. The experimental diets and water were offered *ad libitum*. Parameters measured were Daily Feed Intake (DFI), Initial Live Weight (ILW), Final Live Weight (FLW), Total Weight Gain (TWG) and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR).

2.4 Experimental diets

The experimental diets were identified as treatment 1, 2, 3, and 4 with treatments 2 and 3 containing 5% and 10% Hatchery Waste Meal (HWM) inclusion levels respectively, while treatment 1 and 4 were both control diets devoid of HWM. Treatment 1 contained the same sets of ingredients with similar inclusion levels as those of treatment 2 and 3, while treatment 4 was the most popular brand of commercial feed (Vital feeds) used to serve as the second control diet for the experiment. The diets (1, 2 and 3) contain 20%CP and 2808 kcal /kg ME. The calculated composition of the experimental diets is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Gross and Calculated Composition of the experimental diets

Ingredient	Treatments			
	T ₁ (0%HWM)	T ₂ (5%HWM)	T ₃ (10%HWM)	T ₄ (0%HWM)
Maize	53	52	52	-
Groundnut cake	20	21	19	-
Hatchery waste meal	0	5	10	-
Wheat offal	19	15	12	-
Blood meal	4	3	3	-
Limestone	1.5	1.5	1.7	-
Bone meal	1.5	1.5	1.3	-
Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	-
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	-
Methionine	0.25	0.25	0.25	-
Lysine	0.25	0.25	0.25	-
Total (kg)	100	100	100	100
Calculated Composition				
ME kcal/kg	2808	2802	2805	2900
Crude protein (%)	20.1	20.3	20.1	20.0
Crude fiber (%)	4.1	3.8	3.6	3.5
Calcium (%)	1.4	1.7	2.1	1.0
Phosphorous (%)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Methionine	0.5	0.5	0.5	-
Lysine	1.1	1.2	1.2	-

2.5 Experimental design and statistical analysis

One hundred and twenty (120) birds were assigned to four treatment diets of 30 birds each in a completely randomized design (CRD) and replicated three times with 10 birds per replicate. The data obtained was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the IBM SPSS package and means separation was done using Duncan's multiple ranges test [11].

3.0 Results

3.1 Proximate and some mineral composition of hatchery waste meal

The proximate composition of Hatchery Waste Meal (HWM) is presented in Table 2. Just as expected, the HWM had higher ash content (26.05%) of which calcium is substantially high (7.69%) and phosphorous is of appreciable content (0.43%). The composition of HWM depends on the success of the incubation process. If the incubation process is highly successful, ash content will predominate other constituents.

Table 2: Proximate and some mineral composition of poultry hatchery waste meal

PARAMETERS	VALUES
Crude Protein (%)	23.12
Ether Extract (%)	16.10
Moisture (%)	0.18
Crude Fibre (%)	2.59
Ash (%)	26.05
Nitrogen Free Extract (%)	31.96
Energy (Kcal/Kg)	2182
Ca:P (Ca =7.69; P = 0.43)	17.9:1

3.2 Performance indices of Broiler Chickens

The results on the performance of broiler finisher chicken fed 5% and 10% HWM are presented in Table 2. The results obtained showed that administration of Hatchery Waste Meal (HWM) did not influence daily feed intake of broilers. However, TWG, FBW and FCR were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by inclusion of

HWM. Broilers fed commercial diet (T4: 0% HWM) as the second control had the highest weight gain (1500.00±55.73g) while the lowest (1018.33±55.73g) was observed in birds fed the first control diet (T1: 0% HWM). The first control diet (T1: 0% HWM) had the highest and least desired FCR (2.82±0.12) value among all the

treatments and the most desired FCR (1.83±0.12) was observed in birds fed commercial feed (T4: 0% HWM) as the second control diet. Similarly, the highest and lowest final body weight was observed in the two control treatments, while the treatments with the test ingredient (HWM) had similar final body weight with the highest group.

Table 2: Performance indices of Broiler Finisher fed HWM

Parameters	Treatments				SEM
	T ₁ (0% HWM)	T ₂ (5% HWM)	T ₃ (10% HWM)	T ₄ (0% HWM)	
Initial live weight (g/b)	855.32	856.45	863.68	833.33	5.25
Final live weight (g/b)	1858.33 ^b	2296.67 ^{ab}	1954.00 ^{ab}	2371.67 ^a	90.12
Total weight gain (g/b)	1003.01 ^b	1440.22 ^a	1090.32 ^b	1538.34 ^a	158.83
Daily feed intake (g/b)	131.18	133.90	130.33	118.37	5.53
FCR (g feed g ⁻¹ gain)	2.82 ^a	2.01 ^b	2.60 ^a	1.83 ^b	0.12

abc = mean values along the same row with different superscript are significantly different (p<0.05) FCR=feed conversion ratio SEM= standard error mean

4.0 Discussion

The crude protein value (23.12%) was similar to the 22.8% reported by Ilian and Salman [5], but lower than 44.25% reported by Abiola [7]. The content of dead embryos in relation to eggshells present in the processed HWM [3] and the processing method [14] are possible factors responsible for variations in crude protein. High proportion of eggshell in hatchery waste reduces the CP content [12]. Ash content (26.05%) was higher than 18.12% reported by Abiola et al. [7]. The higher ash content could be due to the high content of egg shell in the whole wastes. Calcium-phosphorus ratio was 17.9:1 which was slightly higher than 16.6:1 reported by Abiola et al. [7]. This ratio is far above the recommended 2:1 for most poultry species which should be balanced to the actual requirements of the birds in question. The high calcium and phosphorus contents of HWM suggests its suitability in meeting the dietary requirements of poultry particularly egg laying birds and broiler chicken that have relatively high requirements of these nutrients. However, metabolizable energy (2182 Kcal Kg⁻¹) was lower than 2706 kcal kg⁻¹ reported by Ilian and Salman [5]. Ether extract (16.10) was lower than 23.94% reported by Abiola et al. [7]. The lower ether extract content of the HWM could be associated with lower egg yolk content of infertile eggs in the whole sample and this is in line with the findings of Abiola et al. [7].

The result on the broiler chicken performance was in line with the findings of Odunsi [3] who reported that feed intake was not significantly (p > 0.05) influenced by hatchery waste containing diets, while weight gain was (p < 0.05) influenced. Similarly, Agunbiade [13] reported that weight gain increases when hatchery waste meal completely replaces fish meal in broiler chicken. However, Mehdipour [6] reported no significant difference (p < 0.05) in weight gain but birds fed 4.5% HWM had higher feed intake than other treatment groups. The difference observed in FCR could be attributed to the variability in the digestibility and bio-availability of nutrients of the experimental diets. The highest FCR indicates more quantity of feed is required to gain corresponding live weight. The results of FCR in the present study partially agree with the findings of Mehdipour [6].

5.0 Conclusion

From the findings of this research, it could be deduced that hatchery wastes meal is rich in energy, crude protein, calcium, phosphorus, and its inclusion in the finisher diet of broiler chickens is beneficial in terms of improved growth and better feed utilization. The utilization of hatchery waste this way, will provide alternative protein and calcium sources in broiler diets and

minimise problem of improper hatchery waste disposal from hatcheries.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations were made:

- i. More research should be conducted to test the effect of hatchery waste meal on the entire growth period of broiler chicken.
- ii. More varied levels of HWM should be tried to determine its optimum inclusion rate for better performance.

7.0 Acknowledgments

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

The Authors declare that they have no conflicting interests.

9.0 References

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